

The Influence of Psychological Well-Being and Self-Efficacy on the Quarter Life Crisis of Early Adult Employees in “X” Institution

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ABSTRACT

Quarter life crisis is a phenomenon that is now quite well known and realized by individuals in early adulthood. This study aims to determine the effect of psychological well-being and self-efficacy on the quarter life crisis of early adult staff at Educational Institution X. The sample in this study was 80 staff of early adult age at Educational Institution X with a sampling technique using purposive sampling. The data collection method uses a psychological well-being scale by Ryff (1995), a self-efficacy, and a quarter life crisis measurement tool by Hassler (2009). The data analysis technique used is multiple regression technique. Based on the research results, the significance coefficient for the self-efficacy variable is 0.000 with $\beta = -0.427$ (or -42.7%). Meanwhile, it is also known that the significance coefficient value for the psychological well-being variable is 0.000 with $\beta = (0.415$ or 41.5%). This shows that these two variables jointly influence the quarter life crisis variable.

Keyword: psychological well-being, self-efficacy, quarter life crisis, adulthood

Introduction

This time, the phenomenon of quarter-life crises is quite often heard (in line with the developing era and the easy-access of society to get information. Because of the easy-access, to get the information, many individuals - especially those who are in early adulthood-start to realize and feel about that crisis. Those in that crisis generally try to adapt to the crises with new responsibilities and roles. There are quite many people who find it difficult to adapt and thus experience crises. The crises they feel often make them worried about their future and easily desperate. Those are especially for individuals in the early adult stage. Quarter-life crises are a phenomenon of emotional crises that take place when someone is in the process of emerging adulthood (Martin, 2016). This phenomenon often happens for employees with or in a stage of early adulthood in a certain institution X. Many of them in that institution know and realize that they are in a crisis. This is when they are adapting to the new roles and responsibilities they are running. These include the responsibility to be a new employee after they graduate, marriage and having a new role as husband/wife, a new parent, and other responsibilities they get in the stage of early adulthood. The employees often worry about the future of familyhood, the careers, to balance them so they can make sure that everything runs well.

There are anxieties; anxiety about failures, and insecurity of one's capabilities, and the employer starts to compare what they achieve and what other people achieve Hurlock (2002). Assume that the tasks of those in the early stage are always the hopes of their close individuals which comprise jobs, choosing a prospective husband or wife, financial independence, and responsibilities. The capabilities to do the tasks for those who are at the early stage of adulthood have impacts on the Capabilities to do the tasks when they are in the mid-stage of adulthood. Those successes in education, Careers, and socializing, are socially admitted. Those will determine prosperity in the future. Thus, these individuals in the early stage of adulthood will have burdens and will be worried about the many developing tasks.

Emerging Adulthood, Arnett (2004) said is experienced by individuals aged between 18 to 29 years old. Arnett stated that the period was a critical period when individuals had to prepare well to face the future because they were demanded to cope with bits of knowledge and skills when they grew up as mature Individuals. This era was described by Arnett to exist when individuals have already completed childhood and adolescence. On the other hand, they are not yet prepared to have individual Capabilities and responsibilities as an adult who tries to develop and get involved more in terms of education, jobs, social relations, love, and the view of the world. For some people, this phase is considered difficult enough in that every individual is indirectly forced to adapt to the new condition together with the consequences. So it is called a crisis. Many of them become depressed because they are not satisfied with the achievements they get and they feel stagnant and find it difficult to appreciate them. Jackson and Warren (200) said that crises have negative impacts on their life, and one of them is stress or depression. Stress piles can create many new problems. related to emotion and behaviors. For example, there are problems of unclear future life, unseen achievements, love, and burdens of responsibilities. However, this crisis is also a phase that forms the individuals to be mature enough to behave, make decisions, and solve problems. It has an impact on the well-being of each individual.

Ryff (1989) defines psychological well-being as a condition when individuals have positive attitudes toward themselves and other people and are able to make decisions about their behaviors, Create and arrange the environment well, and have a purpose in life. and make life more meaningful, and try to explore and develop themselves. Psychological well-being can be seen through a condition when individuals have positive attitudes to their own and other peoples' deeds, and make self-decisions. arrange their own behaviors, and create and arrange the environments. based on their needs, have a purpose in life, make life more meaningful, and try to explore and develop themselves.

Every individual psychological well-being can be seen in the crisis phase. Of course, this phase of crises will determine how every individual is surely successful in what they are doing. It is certain that every individual self-efficacy can be different too. According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy is related to self-belief to accomplish the expected behaviors. This is needed by Individuals because the crisis phase is a flash-back phase where They have gone to an adulthood stage and have new roles.

The insecurity of self-capability is certainly unavoidable, yet many of them struggle to convince others that they can make them true. It was said by Bandura (1997) that a low level of self-efficacy will lead to an increase in anxiety and avoidance behaviors. They don't have the capabilities to manage to make decisions, with special risk, thus, they have a tendency to avoid since they are considered as a threat. The belief of incapacibilities will influence the behaviors they choose, how to do something to achieve their goals, and how long to cope with the obstacles so that they can adapt and solve them according to their choices and purposes.

The research by Mirošsky and Ross as adopted by Tanner and Friends (2008) Compares between the early adulthood period and the progressive steps after. The result shows that individuals aged 20 experienced more depression than others in that they have difficulties in handling socialization problems within themselves and other people. So that they have a reason to find/need professional help. Another research about quarter-life crises done by Robinson, Cimporescu, and Thompson (2020) states the objective is to know the Correlation between quarter-life crisis with depression symptoms and the psychological well-being of university fresh graduates in one of the Universities in London. Robinson and Cimporescu & Thompson's research (2020) used the longitudinal method with 3-step calculation and it lasted for 12 months. This research used psychological well-being. scale with 18 items belonging to Ryff (1995) to measure psychological. CESD-10 (Zhang, 2012), to find depression symptoms and Crises definition question (CDQ) belongs to Robinson (2019) to measure quarter-life crisis. It shows that 61 persons experienced a long crisis period.

Psychological well-being and self-efficacy certainly have impacts on the crisis phase of every individual in the stage of early adulthood. With this research, the researchers want to know the effects of psychological well-being and self-efficacy toward quarter-life crises with the subject of the research of the employer institution X with the adult stage for those who aged 21-28 years.

Method

This research is a quantitative study. The operational definition of quarter-life crisis variables is the individual misgivings to make decisions, desperation feelings, negative judgments, being trapped in a difficult situation, anxiety, depression, and worry about interpersonal relationships (Robbins & Wilner, 2001). Meanwhile, the operational definition of psychological well-being variables is self-acceptance, positive relationship with others, autonomy, environment management, the purpose of life, and self-development (Ryff, 1389). The last, the definition of self-efficacy variables is self-confidence in an uncertain and stressful situation, the confidence in handling problems and obstacles, the ability to achieve the expected target, the confidence in the ability to increase motivation, cognitive Skills and establish the actions to achieve a certain result (Bandura 1977).

The statistical analytical method used is a double linear regression technique. This is a regression technique that involves more than one independent variable. Double-linear regression analyses aim at knowing which direction and how big the effect of the Independent Variable is on a dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018) if the probability result shows a significant value smaller than $0.05 < 0.05$, the independent variable is believed to have roles to the dependent variable. Data analyses are wholly done using the application IBM SPSS Statistic Data for Windows 22.0. Samples of the research are all employees in the early adulthood stage in Institution X as many as 80 employees. The technique to get the sample uses purposive sampling which is taking - sample technique by determining certain criteria. (Sugiono, 2008). Data-taking method uses a scale of psychological well-being by Ryff (1995). self-efficacy scale and a measurement tool for quarter-life crises by Hassler (2009). The reliability test used in this research is Coefficient Cronbach Alpha. The questionnaire is said to be valid or reliable if the score of Cronbach Alpha is bigger than 0,60 (Hartono, 2011).

Result And Discussion

Based on Descriptive analyses for quarter-life crisis data can be seen in Table 1. It shows that the empirical mean ($\pi = 74,24$) is lower than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 75$), meaning that the psychological well-being of employees in institution X is in the moderate category. Empirical descriptive analyses for self-efficacy data show that the empirical mean ($\pi = 40.37$) is lower than the hypothetic ($\mu = 30$). It shows that self-efficacy belonging to the employees in the early adulthood stage in Institution X takes in the high category.

Table 1. Mean and Descriptive Subject Category

Variable	Empirical Mean	Hypothetical Mean	Category
<i>Psychological Well-Being</i>	59.1	54	Moderate
<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	40.37	30	High
<i>Quarter Life Crisis</i>	74.24	37	Moderate

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The calculation result of the mean age of respondents is known and found that there are differences in psychological well-being, self-efficacy, and quarter-life crises among the research respondents. The result and category based on age can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Mean and Category based on the Age of Participants

Age	<i>Psychological Well-Being</i>	<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	<i>Quarter Life Crisis</i>
21-25	59.1 (Moderate)	40.37 (High)	74.24 (Moderate)
26-30	60.2 (Moderate)	30.29 (Moderate)	131.2 (Very High)

On the basis of the normality test to the variable of quarter-life crises stated in Table 3, it shows that p is counted as 0,200, the variable of psychological well-being shows p as 0,016 and the variable of self-efficacy shows p as 0,200. Data distribution is said to be normal if the significant value is bigger than 0,05 ($p > 0,05$). It means that the variables of quarter-life crises and self-efficacy are normally distributed (symmetrical) while the variables of psychological well-being are not normally distributed (asymmetrical). The test result of linearity shows linear-connected data, with the result of linearity $p < 0.05$. referring to the linearity model which is appropriate to apply and the result also shows the result of deviation from linearity $p > 0,05$ which means that the data can be said linearly connected.

Table 3. Result of Normality Test to Quarter-Life Crisis

Variable	Sig.
<i>Psychological Well-Being</i>	.016
<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	.200
<i>Quarter Life Crisis</i>	.200

The hypothetical test is also carried out using the double regression method. The result analyses of dimension regression of Quarter life-crises stated in the table indicate that the variables of psychological well-being and self-efficacy concurrently affect Quarter life crises. The result of double-regression analysis assumes that the process of value $F = 23.193$ with significance level 0,0000 ($p > 0.05$), value R Square 0.376 (37°). This means that psychological well-being and self-efficacy impact as much as 371% and the rest 63% are affected by other factors outside the research. The result of the study also indicates that psychological well-being is in the moderate category. Meanwhile, self-efficacy in the high category affects the quarter-life crises of the employees in early adulthood in the institution "X".

Table 4. The Result of Regression Test Psychological Well-Being Toward Quarter-Life Crisis

F	Sig.	R	R Square
23.193	0.000	0.613	0.376

In Table 5, we know that the significance coefficient For Self-efficacy variables is 0.000 with B = -0.427 (or -42.7%). Meanwhile, it is known that the significance coefficient value of variable psychological well-being is 0.000 with B = (0,415 or 41,5%). This shows that both variables jointly impact quarter-life crises. The result of the study proves that psychological well-being and self-efficacy have impacts on quarter 21-25 years resulting in life crises since this study on the psychological employees' aged well-being with moderate category and self-efficacy with high category and quarter-life crises with moderate category. On the employees aged between 26-30 years, it results in psychological well-being with moderate Category and self-efficacy with moderate category quarter-life crisis with very high category.

Table 5. Regression Coefficient of Psychological Well-Being and Self-Efficacy on Quarter Life Crisis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	40.571	23.039		1.761	.082
<i>Psychological Well-Being</i>	1.483	.323	.415	4.597	.000
<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	-1.372	.290	-.427	-4.730	.000

Psychological well-being and self-efficacy can affect quarter-life crisis. Robinson (2018) said that individuals start to ask about life, feel stagnant and lack motivation, worry about whether or not to leave their comfort zone, are not happy with their achievements, feel uncertain, and depressed with the environment, and start to compare with others. Those with crises are not able to optimize self-potential in self-development. The failure according to Robinson (2018), has impacts on self-esteem, affecting the positive and psychological well-being of individuals. Another empirical study also explains that besides psychological well-being, self-efficacy, also takes a big role in crisis conditions experienced by individuals in early adulthood. (Walshe, 2018; Afnan, 2019). Individuals with a lack of self-confidence in their capability to manage the situation now, and not having the capability to plan actions to achieve

the goals will experience a crisis. According to Walshe (2018), the Crises of individuals in early adulthood have emotional intelligence, self-esteem, and low self-efficacy.

Given impacts, both variables are not the main factors in quarter-life crises. This can be seen in Table 4 stating that the value of R square is 0.376 (37°). It can be said that both variables Impact quarter-life crises as much as 37% and 63% of it are the other factors. Another factor from the quarter-life crisis happening with individuals at the early adulthood level is caused by family pressure, problems with the peer-friends, feeling insecurity about the future, being disappointed with self-capabilities, frustration with the relations with others, or work pressures. Factors such as culture or social norms in the society also can cause individuals a quarter life crisis. For example, close relatives and close friends can affect an individual perception of facing problems and how to solve their problems. The more demands they have, the more they start to feel the emotion and negative perceptions about themselves. However, there are positive dimension they have, but they do not realize the impacts of creativity and bothering social functions (Fitri, 2019).

Another factor forming quarter-life crises is self-awareness (Auzoult & Massart, 2014) (Martanian, 2020). The research by Auzoult & Massart (2014) stated that individuals with a lack of self-awareness like capabilities to comprehend, accept, and manage all self-potential, will not be able to control all emotions which can benefit them to make good relationships with other people.

Ideally, growing up Individuals should have been independent. Compared to those who still depend on their parents (Arnett, 2014), one of the ways to make them independent is their separation from their parents and they live separately (Arnett, 2014). Yet the study result shows that 92% of subjects still live with their parents rather than live alone or with friends (Blieszner & Roberto, 2012). The phenomenon found in Institution X is that the employees aged 21-25 years still live with their parents, and they are not married yet. Meanwhile, employees aged 26-30 have already been married and lived separately with their parents but they have a bigger responsibility than those who are still with their parents.

According to the scale calculation result, the empirical mean in Table 2 categorizes quarter-life crisis based on the age divisions, the employees in Institution X with early adulthood category with the age of 26-30 years have higher or very high category compared to those with the age of 21-25 who are immoderate category. This is supported by research conducted by Pinggolio (2015) that stress caused by expectations not in line with the reality of the jobs and relations has been found as a factor that contributes to quarter-life crises in early

adulthood. In the field, practically the married employees who are already parents and have worked quite long in the institution " X" are considered the employees with early adulthood aged between 26-30 years. As a result, the employees aged between 26-30 have a higher category of quarter-life crisis compared to those aged between 21-25.

Conclusion

Based on the research result, it can be concluded that both variables that are psychological well-being and self-efficacy have impacts on quarter-life crises. Yet both variables are not the main factors that cause quarter-life crisis. Other factors which lead to quarter-life crises are external factors such as parents' expectations and social standards.

The employees in the early adulthood category aged 26-30 have higher quarter-life crises than those aged 21-25 years. This result is supported by the condition of the employees aged 26-30 who have been married and have children. Thus, in line with the growing ages, the worries or anxieties related to life goals, careers, and responsibilities are increasing. In this case, it can cause an increase of quarter-life crisis.

Suggestion

This study has described the results of the research from three variables and the interrelation among them. The next researcher may be able to analyze quarter-life crises with other factors such as external factors. He/she is also able to analyze more or elaborate on how big the internet factors and external factors affect the quarter-life crisis. Besides, the researcher can accommodate using more samples. Hence, the study can represent the observed population.

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